

LEGAL-CRIMINAL POSITION OF MINORS IN THE REPUBLIC OF KOSOVO AFTER 1999

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Abstract

By juvenile delinquency, we mean the antisocial and illegal behavior of minors. Young age is chosen with favorable rates in many countries. Usually, she does age 14-18 years. However, in the criminal-material, procedural and criminological literature, the term juvenile delinquency or young people's criminal behavior is often used. It is desired to emphasize the criminal activity of young people, which includes both juveniles and adults. Thus, the notion of youth criminality is used to emphasize criminal activity for all young people, regardless of age. In some cases, you also belong to the juvenile as a delinquent person, because there is a connection between the entire youth population, no matter what stage of age it is, from a biopsy and socio-cultural point of view, it has not yet been formed and therefore, a special approach and treatment is needed.

Keywords: Delinquency, Criminal law, Juvenile, Preventive.

INTRODUCTION

By juvenile delinquency, we mean the anti-social and illegal behaviors of minors. Young age is set at favorable rates in many countries. Usually, it covers the age of 14-18 years. However, in the criminal-material, procedural and criminological literature, the term juvenile delinquency or young people's criminal behavior is often used. It is desirable to emphasize the criminal activity of young people, including both juveniles and adults. So, the notion of youth criminality is used to emphasize all young people's criminal activity, regardless of age.

In some cases, juveniles are included as delinquents because there is a belief that the entire population of young people, no matter what age it is, has not yet been formed in biopsy and socio-cultural terms. And therefore, a special approach and treatment are needed. This slightly broader understanding of juvenile delinquency finds more application in criminological and sociological treatments and studies, and less in criminal law. According to criminal law concepts, this issue is differentiated and regulated in a way accurate and concrete through criminal provisions where certain ages and categories are defined. Therefore, it is also related to their criminal responsibility and the application of various sanctions.

METHODOLOGY

The scientific treatment of juveniles' legal-criminal and criminological position requires the application of appropriate methods for the realization of the goals set out in the scientific paper.

Achieving the purpose of this paper necessarily requires applying appropriate methods that enable the provision of proper data. Therefore, in our research, we will apply:

- Theoretical methodology (legal method, historical method, comparative method, sociological, psychological and logical method); and
- Empirical methodology (statistical methods - method of the law of large numbers, model method, method of correlation, mean, percentage; methods of analysis and synthesis; method of observation and descriptive method, method of shame, Survey, and interview).
- Scientific Studies (Self-Accusation Study, Victimization Study, ISRD)

The application of these methods enables us to assess the situation as it is, analyze and evaluate the practices of bodies and institutions in dealing with this phenomenon, and what needs to be done in the future to expand knowledge on the causes, forms, and ways of combating behaviors. Such (Delegate lata, Delegate free).

In this paper, we are based on a register of bibliographic sources and classical and current contemporary literature in the country and in the world in general, consulting papers, monographs, and material research of various projects and conferences in the country and the world.

In this aspect, comparative statistical data on the phenomenon of juvenile delinquency in the region or the world, in general, are used separately.

Definition of juvenile delinquency

The issue of defining juvenile delinquency is as complicated as it is complex. This complexity conditions the necessity of treating juvenile delinquency as a legal-criminal and adequate criminological, sociological, and psychological treatment.

In this context, to define juvenile delinquency means to elaborate on the criminological, sociological, criminological-political, criminal-legal, psychological, criminological aspect, and other aspects of this problem, explaining at the same time the certain phenomena of delinquent juvenile delinquency, where these behaviors are often confused with the notion of adult delinquency.

It should be said first that juvenile delinquency is among the many negative phenomena that characterize a society. Delinquency as a negative phenomenon of juveniles is as old as society itself. Being always present was less and was more influenced, of course, by the processes or developments that have characterized society in general, the environment, and the closest circle they have lived before. In a word, delinquency is closely related to society's circumstances, namely those related to economic development, which consequently has the state and position of the family, as well as the socio-cultural characteristics of a given society.

Delinquency as a phenomenon is found in almost all definitions, theoretical, empirical, and legal, defined as minors' behavior that conflicts with a society with moral, ethical, customary, religious, and legal norms.

As for the term delinquency, in Latin, we see that this expression means error or guilt, and from this, we can say that delinquency means a bad, anti-social, erroneous behavior of minors, and as such responsible for a minor.

So, by juvenile delinquency, we mean the anti-social and illegal behaviors of minors. The positive norms of many states set at a young age. Usually, it covers the age of 14-18 years. However, in the criminological literature, the term juvenile delinquency or criminal behavior of young people is often used, in which case it is desirable to emphasize the criminal activity of young people, which includes both juveniles and adults, young people. So, the notion of youth criminality is used to emphasize all young people's criminal activity, regardless of age. In some cases, juveniles are included as delinquents because there is a belief that the entire population of young people, no matter what age they are, is still not formed in biopsychological and socio-cultural terms and, therefore, a special approach and treatment is needed. This slightly broader understanding of juvenile delinquency finds more application in criminological and sociological treatments and studies, and less in criminal law. According to criminal law concepts, this issue is differentiated and regulated in a way accurate and concrete through criminal provisions where certain ages and categories are defined. Therefore, this is also related to their criminal responsibility and the application of various sanctions.

Kosovo Juvenile Justice Code

The Juvenile Justice Code in Kosovo (KDM) has defined the principles and definitions of juvenile, juvenile, and adult notions.

The basic characteristic of juvenile delinquency in contemporary society is that it is not increasing to improve and manifest with the form of presentation that is quite dangerous, for which juvenile delinquency today is one of the best concerns for all societies and done. This has been done in the first place with the school's study and analysis and the resources that lead to juvenile delinquency. On the other hand, notice the effort and action, find the method, the most appropriate means, and ways to prevent it.

The meaning of the term juvenile or juvenile delinquent in the legislation of Kosovo

Juveniles represent a particular category in criminal law, who can be presented as perpetrators of various criminal offenses, in general crime with one country during their biological, psychological, and social development. Juvenile offenders do not differ much from adults in the types and forms of criminal offenses. But they differ in that, at the time of the commission of the criminal offense, they are at a sensitive stage in developing their personality, during which stage they do not fully control their actions.

The way society reacts in relation to them, as perpetrators of criminal offenses, can positively or negatively affect their personality development. To tarnish and unlabeled them, as well as the tendency of society, that in the future they are useful members of it, their antisocial actions in the criminal law literature, are called juvenile delinquency.

The term delinquency means all actions and behaviors of minors prohibited by the positive legal provisions of a country, which are designated as offenses. These actions and behaviors

represent concrete violations and violations of some positive legal norms, which can be criminal, misdemeanor, economic, and disciplinary. Therefore, these negative antisocial and criminal acts committed by juveniles are often called juvenile delinquency.

Throughout the historical development of criminal law, juveniles have had special treatment compared to adults in committing a criminal offense, which treatment has been enjoyed by juveniles in Kosovo during the historical development of criminal law provisions.

According to Albanian customary law, the perpetrator of a criminal offense is a person who can carry a rifle, and such is considered a person aged 12-15 years, at which age is deemed to be irresponsible.

Albanian canon law

Albanian customary law had failed to divide juveniles into particular categories and could not impose measures and other punishments on juvenile offenders, other than the sentences provided for adult perpetrators.

After the Ottoman Empire's capitulation, Kosovo and other ethnic areas were occupied by Yugoslavia, called the Kingdom of Serbia, Croatia, and Slovenia, a state founded in 1918.

In 1929, Yugoslavia issued its own Criminal Code, which regulates in its entirety the legal-criminal treatment of juvenile offenders. According to this Code, juveniles were divided into two categories; young juveniles (14-17 years old) and adult juveniles (17-21 years old). Young juveniles could be held criminally liable if they understood the importance of their offense and control their behavior. Certain educational measures could be imposed on such juveniles, while the sentences were only exceptional if it was a recidivist.

Adult juveniles were considered criminally liable, and sentences could be imposed on them, but special provisions were provided for sentencing.

After the Second World War, the provisions for juvenile delinquents were provided for in the Law on Types of Sentences of 1945 and in the general part of the Criminal Code of 1946. Criminal Code of 1951.

According to the Criminal Code of the former Yugoslavia of 1951, juveniles were divided into two categories, namely; Young children (14-16 years old) and adult juveniles (16-18 years old). According to this Code, juveniles could not be sentenced to death and some types of sentences. Also, the age of minors has been foreseen as a mandatory mitigating circumstance when sentencing in 1959 changes were made to the Criminal Code of 1951. In the first place, the changes consisted of the fact that educational measures were considered the main types of criminal sanctions. Sentences for young juveniles could not be imposed, while for adult juveniles, only exceptionally could juvenile imprisonment be imposed.

With the Constitution of the former Yugoslavia of 1974, legislative powers in the field of criminal legislation were divided at the level of the Federation and the Republic and the two Autonomous Provinces as constitutive units. With this Constitution, Kosovo enjoys the status of an Autonomous Province. Following the concept of decentralization of criminal legislation, the

legal-criminal treatment of juvenile perpetrators of criminal offenses was regulated by the Criminal Code of the former Yugoslavia and the Criminal Code of Kosovo. These laws, which entered into force on July 1, 1977, and which were applied until April 5, 2004. Respectively with the entry into force of the Criminal Code of Kosovo on April 6, 2004, ceased to apply the Criminal Law of the former Yugoslavia and the Criminal Law of Kosovo of 1977.

According to these laws, perpetrators under the age of 14 are considered children, and no measures or penalties provided by criminal law could be imposed on them. Juveniles were divided into two categories. In young juveniles, 14-16 years old, adult juveniles up to 16-18 years old. Therefore, according to the abovementioned criminal laws, juveniles could be imposed: disciplinary measures, educational measures, imprisonment for juveniles, etc. Also some types of special obligations along with added supervision.

Young juveniles are not considered criminally liable. Only educational measures could be imposed on them.

Also, juvenile adults have not been considered criminally liable and educational measures have been imposed on them. However, despite this principled choice, adult minors could exceptionally be held criminally liable. In such cases, if the special conditions are met, the adult juvenile may be sentenced to juvenile imprisonment.

According to the above-mentioned laws, in certain cases, educational measures could be imposed on adult perpetrators of criminal offenses, who at the time of committing the criminal offense, have not reached 21 years of age.

After Kosovo's liberation on June 12, 1999, the need arose to build new legislation compatible with Western European standards. In the framework of the laws that had to be prepared due to the necessity of fighting crime and the rule of law, the UNMIK administration first started the work to prepare the Criminal Code and the Code of Criminal Procedure. In the spirit of the contemporary concept of the most consistent incarnations or criminal law for juveniles. During the Criminal Code preparation, it was decided that the criminal legal treatment of juvenile offenders be separated from the Criminal Code and regulated by a special law.

The Juvenile Justice Code was approved on April 20, 2004, and entered into force on the same day. Thus, for the first time in Kosovo's history, similar to other Western European countries, the issue of criminal-legal treatment of juvenile offenders and criminal offenses was regulated by a special law.

It should be emphasized that in the Juvenile Justice Code (ICM) of Kosovo, as a platform and concrete choices are accepted a number of conventions and other relevant international acts, which are dedicated to the protection of children, their freedoms and rights. . In the framework of these conventions, concrete principles and solutions have been accepted separately from the set of minimum United Nations rules regarding the administration of juvenile justice—known as the Beijing Rules of November 20, 1985, the Tokyo Rules on Alternative Measures and Sanctions of 14.12.1990 and the Convention on the Rights of the Child of 20.11 1989. The

General Assembly also approves all three of these acts and the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women of the United Nations.

As a positive right, KDM, in the Republic of Kosovo, which entered into force in 2010, for the first time, removed juveniles as perpetrators of criminal offenses from the criminal legislation, which is attributed to significant perpetrators of crimes.

This KDM Code laid the foundations of a new juvenile procedural and penal system, compatible with the new political system and international democratic standards.

In contemporary societies, including our society in the fight against juvenile delinquency, pedagogical, educational measures should be dominant. This enables the positive development of the juvenile personality, social and family problems, professional training, and the guarantee of perspective. However, in addition to preventive measures, every society is obliged to impose criminal measures and sanctions on juvenile perpetrators of criminal offenses. Their concept and composition differ from the measures and sanctions imposed on major perpetrators of criminal offenses.

According to the Juvenile Justice Code KDM in the Republic of Kosovo for juveniles, the meaning of the term juvenile or juvenile delinquent regulates the procedure of imposition and execution of measures and sentences against juveniles, court procedure and mediation procedure for juveniles.

In order to get an adequate view of what we call juveniles according to KDM, in the following, we will offer some notions of juveniles as delinquents and how we can understand them as adequately as possible to come to the implementation of this code.

Definitions, expressions used in this juvenile criminal code have the following meanings:

Minors - a person who has not reached the age of eighteen (18) years. It means that any person up to the age of 18, who according to the Convention on the Rights of the Child is considered a minor, and in our juvenile justice code we have provided;

Juvenile - a person between the ages of fourteen (14) and eighteen (18) years, this age is defined because any action of a minor at this age has criminal liability;

Young minor - person between the ages of fourteen (14) and sixteen (16) years. If we look above, according to the Juvenile Justice Code KDM, we have a division of 14-18 years old and now comes the next division 14-16 years old; the young juvenile is the juvenile who during the time of committing the act that is legally qualified as a criminal offense, he has reached the age of fourteen, while he has not reached the age of sixteen. Persons at this age are still in the stage of psychophysical development, and criminal responsibility is still debatable. The division aims to differentiate between sanctioning and juveniles as perpetrators of a criminal offense at the age of 14-16 years.

b) Adult juvenile - a person between the ages of sixteen (16) and eighteen (18), is a juvenile who at the time of committing the act which by law is considered a criminal offense, for which a fine or imprisonment for up to three years or misdemeanor, has reached sixteen years, and

has not reached eighteen years or who is addicted to drugs, psychotropic substances or alcohol, juveniles with developmental disabilities and juveniles, abandoned in terms of education and the society that is in such a situation in which the realization of the educational function of the family is difficult or impossible, which due to such conditions is or may be contrary to the law; a person at this age according to KDM we see that he has a more pronounced responsibility even though he is in psychophysical development, and if we look at the KDM and the Criminal Code of Kosovo in sanctioning, these age groups have more severe sanction than the above age groups.

Young adult - person between the ages of eighteen (18) and twenty-one (21) years. Is a person who at the time of the trial for a criminal offense has reached the age of eighteen, while he has not reached the age of twenty-one, the sanction is a legal consequence of the criminal offense related to the deprivation or restriction of certain freedoms and rights of juveniles due to the criminal offense imposed by the court in a procedure determined by this law; the person who has turned 18, is an adult and we see that in KDM it is foreseen as a young juvenile because we start from the fact of personality development, some have stagnation, and some have progressed in personality development in different age groups.

Adult - a person who has reached the age of eighteen (18) years.

Thus, the notion of juvenile delinquency (juvenile delinquency) is used to emphasize the criminal activity of all juveniles, regardless of age. In some cases, this includes children as delinquent persons who, according to the Juvenile Justice Code, call the person from birth to 18 years because there is a belief that the entire population of juveniles, regardless of what age stages they are, from a biopsychological and sociocultural point of view, has not yet been formed and therefore, a special approach and treatment is needed. The definitions defined above for juvenile delinquency are more applicable in criminological and sociological treatments and studies, and less in the criminal-legal one, because, according to the legal-criminal concepts, this issue is differentiated and regulated in a precise way and concrete through criminal provisions where certain ages and categories are defined. Therefore, this is also related to their criminal responsibility and the application of various sanctions.

The socio-economic and political position of juveniles as perpetrators of delinquent behavior

The problems of free movement of citizens as a fundamental human right (non-liberalization of visas, modern educational and socializing opportunities for young people, exchange of practices and experiences among young people, etc.), have affected young people The Republic of Kosovo to be in a wrong position, desirable compared to their age groups in the region and beyond.

The socio-economic position of juveniles in the Republic of Kosovo vis-à-vis organized crime groups operating in Kosovo and the regions is endangered as a current situation because juveniles have been offered an opportunity to become part of these criminal groups through recruitment and their education in the field of crime in general and trafficking of all age groups in the Republic of Kosovo, in the countries of the European Union.

Tab.1.Indicators of age groups by years

Years	Age	Years	Age
2006	14	2012	20
2007	15	2013	21
2008	16	2014	22
2009	17	2015	23
2010	18	2016	24
2011	19		

From 2006 to 2016, several years have passed, and if we look at the table above, we notice that young people who in 2006 were 14 years old then in 2016 are 24 years old. According to this, we come to the conclusion that young people through these years at what stage of their age and in which calendar year they have been more and were less delinquent.

As a result of juveniles' behavior starting from their socio-economic position from 2006 to 2016, we see, according to the table below, how many have been convicted in total by years.

Tab.2.Convicted juveniles aged 16-18 years, 2006-2016

Years	Punished	Years	Punished
2006	665	2012	474
2007	648	2013	786
2008	719	2014	840
2009	686	2015	568
2010	339	2016	760
2011	375		

According to the table above, I have tried to provide data about juveniles who in 2006 were 14 years old and in 2016 are 23 years old, which means that this data is an indicator of the comparison of juveniles as delinquents in per year and their change by age. If we look at the table that juveniles aged 14 and 15 years respectively in 2006-07 when they reached the age of 16 years respectively in 2008, the percentage of delinquency and sentences for juveniles increases by 37%, and the question arises what were the treatments of these age groups through the years marked above, how we treated these juveniles and what are the advantages and consequences of them and share them. Suppose we have to provide adequate data on the consequences of treatment and what is the position of a minor in the Republic of Kosovo, where socio-economic and political problems have hampered their position in the Republic of Kosovo. In that case, we can take the year 2013-2015, the exodus of many young people, the illegal crossing of the borders of the Balkan countries and those of the EU.

Example:

- 1) Sample - 18,000 left from the Republic of Kosovo.
- 2) Exodus Prishtina-Belgrade-Novu Sad-Hungary-EU.

- 3) Age group 8 to 12 (5%), 12 to 14 (7%), 14 to 16 (2%), 16 to 18 (21%), 18 to 25 (45%), and from 25 - (20%).
- 4) Socio-economic situation 75% never unemployed.
- 5) Education - primary school 23%, secondary education (55%), higher education (18%) without answers (4%).

According to the above data, we conclude that the age group of juveniles 14 years old was in 2006, and if compared to 2015, these juveniles are 19 years old, which means that the highest percentage of departure is in the age group 18 to 25 years.

According to data from national statistics of the Police, Prosecution, Courts and correctional institutions and data obtained from the research, whether national or international, through the Study of Self-Accusation and Victimization (SVV), within the Association of Kosovo Criminologists (KASK), as International project International Self-Report of Delinquency (ISRD), we conclude that although the difficult socio-economic situation, the position of juveniles in terms of criminal law and criminology is relative compared to data compared in the regions, the data which show us that juvenile delinquent behavior is increasing and especially when we do the analysis in age groups and gender remain worrying.

From the data of the forums and specialized bodies of the United Nations and associations dealing with crime tracking, it is noticed that during the last decades, the participation of juveniles in organized crime groups, juveniles in committing crimes has significantly increased. And various criminal behaviors and with whom to see that juveniles are in a position of social and economic competition between them.

According to national evidence by the police, prosecution, and court, it is increasing and usually ranges from 5-15%.

The participation of juveniles in some criminal offenses, in the total number of criminal offenses, is often very high, this percentage ranges from 15-35%. This figure is worrying because this turnout is really high. This percentage of juvenile participation in crime is usually observed in property crimes, crimes of violence, consumption, and illicit drug trafficking and prostitution. There is also an increase in juvenile delinquent behavior in Kosovo. Thus, according to the data presented by the national statistics of jurisprudence, the Department of Justice, it turns out that in Kosovo by juveniles in 2006 nationwide, 1386 criminal offenses were committed by juveniles, while in 2015 nationwide, 865 criminal offenses were committed by minors. Most of these works have been carried out in large urban centers such as:

1. Prishtina 296, 2. Prizren 298, 3. Gjilan 250, 4. Peja 91, 5. Gjakova 76 etc.

The juvenile justice system aims at the welfare of the juvenile and ensures that any reaction to juvenile perpetrators is always in proportion to the circumstances of the perpetrator and the offense. Juvenile perpetrators are given diversity measures and educational measures, as needed. Deprivation of liberty is imposed only as a last resort and should be limited to the shortest possible time.

During deprivation of liberty, a juvenile is offered education, psychological assistance, as needed, and medical assistance to facilitate his or her rehabilitation.

Based on the above factors and remembering that juveniles are in the physical and mental development of personality, therefore when a juvenile commits a delinquent (a criminal offense), according to contemporary law provide for special treatment of them, the purpose of this treatment comes to the juvenile as the perpetrator of the delinquent offense to be given the opportunity of re- socialization and compensation of previously issued education, in order to be part of contemporary society.

Theoretical and practical problems in dealing with the legal-criminal position of juveniles

Juvenile delinquency is a social phenomenon that is manifested by non-compliance with moral and legal norms. It has always existed and emerged, where less and were more, depending on changes in society and the environment in which young people have lived. Delinquency is a type of behavior contrary to certain social norms. A delinquent is an individual who, by his actions, not only violates the norms of the environment but also violates the rights and freedoms of another and falls directly into conflict with others. Juvenile delinquency does not appear suddenly and unexpectedly, but there is a preparatory stage that begins with antisocial behavior from puberty. It is known that growth is a very dynamic process, the most intense period in human life, which is characterized by many emotional changes, with the acquisition of knowledge and the adoption of different habits, attitudes, judgments, and values. No juvenile experiences these changes in the same way. Some manage to manage them well, while some cannot cope with them, which often serves as the cause of their antisocial behavior. Antisocial behaviors of juveniles at this age are many and varied. They appear in a wide range such as stubbornness, insults and swearing, beatings, disobedience and impatience, theft, running away from home and school, etc. If proper measures are not taken to eliminate them at this age, they slowly grow and multiply and become the optimal potential for true delinquency. Scientific research makes it clear that juvenile detention in institutions is a very painful process for any juvenile; this action as a measure damages the development of the juvenile and has the opposite effect on his socialism. It is also generally accepted that denial of liberty is rarely an effective measure in terms of rehabilitation, reintegration and prevention of further violations.

Fig1. Classification and criminal responsibilities by age

The rights of minors are defined by the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, which was adopted in 1989 as the first international treaty dealing with the full protection of minors' rights. The Convention is a guide on how minors should be treated and protected. A special international body of the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child monitors the Convention's implementation in the states that have ratified it. The Convention on the Rights of the Child is for all those who work with minors who come into direct or indirect contact with minors: parents, teachers, educators, senior government officials, care workers, health and social workers, lawyers, judges, police officers. The Convention is also dedicated to minors. Minors need to know their rights from birth. If they are committed to respecting their rights, juveniles develop a sense of responsibility for respecting others' rights. When they participate in decision making, they learn to take responsibility for their own realization. By recognizing and committing to their rights, juveniles become aware that these rights belong to others and in these cases, should not violate them. In accordance with these principles, a juvenile in conflict with the law must enjoy full respect for human rights, guaranteed by the constitution, law, and applicable international regulations, as all juveniles under the jurisdiction of the State concerned.

Juvenile delinquents are classified in several groups in several different countries according to their positive laws, where they define the age categories and regulate a range of issues about their criminal responsibility, about the application of various measures, especially educational-correctional measures. When we talk about juveniles, then we need to know what the age limit is for juveniles and why this limit has been set, because depending on the age, the issue of criminal responsibility, the imposition of educational measures is raised- correctional, the imposition of other sentences and educational-correctional treatment in educational-correctional institutions. As the lowest limit of the age of juveniles and their qualification as perpetrators of criminal behavior, in some countries of the modern world, is taken the age as: a. 7-year (Burma, Ceylon, Egypt, India, Iraq, and several other countries); b. 9-year-old, as the minimum age of criminal responsibility, is taken in Israel, Jordan, Philippines, etc .; c. ten years is considered the age of criminal responsibility in Bolivia, Paraguay, and several other Latin American countries; d. Turkey and Iran, as age and lower age limit, take 11 years; e. Greece, Panama and some other countries, 12 years old, while France and Poland, 13 years old.

In most European countries such as: Austria, Italy, Hungary, Albania, the former Yugoslavia, the lowest limit of criminal responsibility is 14 years old. On the other hand, Switzerland, Denmark, Sweden, as the lowest age takes the age of 15 years. Finland and Chile, meanwhile, require 16 years as the minimum age for juvenile delinquency. The Juvenile Criminal Law of Kosovo in Article 2, paragraph 1, points 1-5, has defined and defined the different ages of juveniles as participants in delinquent activities.

Different names of perpetrators from the ranks of minors

From the findings of well-known perpetrators in juvenile delinquency, we encounter different names of juvenile offenders.

At the beginning, we noticed that it is necessary to determine who is a juvenile and how he is named, and when he is a delinquent, this means that juveniles as perpetrators of illegal, delinquent offenses are divided into different age groups to be named as perpetrators or parts of the juvenile group as delinquent groups.

Thus, from the research data and in the field of judicial practice, it is noticed that juvenile delinquents are significantly involved in crime against property, a crime against life and body, traffic safety, committing crimes in groups and groups of organized crime, in the activity around the distribution and consumption of narcotics, in other acts of physical or psychological violence, especially in crimes against life and body and in sexual offenses. Looking at all these deviant behaviors by juveniles, we notice that they are divided hierarchically through the designations of personality and the designation of the delinquent action group, it is especially emphasized that such delinquent actions of juveniles are in constant expansion. During the performance of such actions, there is rudeness and pronounced use of violence during the commission of a criminal offense and violent escort of any criminal activity. In different countries, these groups of minors and adults are given different names. Often, these delinquent groups and gangs of minors are distinguished from each other, in terms of style and manner of dress, in terms of special means of committing offenses, in terms of the use of vehicles with which they circulate, etc. These groups and criminal youth organizations have special popular names, in England, they are called "Teddy Boys" or "Teddy Girls", in France, these groups are called "Bluzons Noir", in Italy, they are called "Viteloni", in Poland, under the name "Hooligan", in Japan, under the name "Tojozaki", in Germany "Halstarke", in the USA "Gangs". Such criminal and delinquent groups exist in almost all contemporary countries and states. Recently, these groups of young people are also involved in other criminal activities, e.g., with terrorist activities on ethnic, racial, and religious grounds. Such groups of minors and young people are present in Russia, Germany, Serbia, Syria, Afghanistan, etc. In addition to other criminal activities, these groups also deal with the mistreatment and persecution of members of other national and ethnic peoples and groups. In their criminal actions, they start from racist, chauvinist, and ultra-extreme motives.

These groups have different names and have a special dress and haircut e.g. Skinheads It is thought that the causes of juvenile delinquency are similar to the causes of adult delinquency, but the literature highlights some factors that are somewhat more typical of this age of juvenile delinquency. Thus, especially as factors are mentioned: family environment, family upbringing, the process of education and training, and the impact of the mass media, especially the impact of the revival press, television, film, and literature. In particular, it should be noted that the cause of juvenile delinquency is an inadequate treatment in educational and correctional facilities and other institutions where juveniles are re-educated. For this reason, recidivism and the repetition of juvenile delinquency through various individuals and groups are present.

Some of the names of minors in Kosovo: Falcons, Dardanians, Mahalla, Cucumbers, Plastics, Plisat, Torcida, Intellectuals, etc. As mentioned above, the groups are also sports fan groups, which in certain cases and moments, pass the security measures and, with their actions, cause endanger and cause material and personal damage.

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